

**THE EVOLUTION OF SOCIAL AND
INTERNATIONAL POLICIES WITH THE RISING OF
SOCIAL MEDIA AND GEN-Z ADVOCACY EFFORTS**

By

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Abstract

This research paper examines the evolution of social and international policies in response to the rising influence of social media and Gen-Z advocacy efforts. Generation Z, born after 1996, has faced unique challenges such as post-9/11 wars, climate change, COVID-19, and gun violence. Utilizing platforms like TikTok and Instagram, Gen-Z has leveraged social media to amplify their voices and advocate for social change on a global scale. The primary research question explores the impact of social media on young activists and how these platforms facilitate the traction of social movements. The study utilizes qualitative data from news articles, interviews, and case studies, as well as empirical data on movement outcomes and social media metrics. The findings demonstrate the significant role of social media in connecting, educating, and mobilizing Gen-Z activists, and the implications for policymakers, educators, and social media platforms are discussed.

Introduction

From advocating for human rights in Sub-Saharan Africa, pushing for climate change policies on the streets of New York City, and protesting gun violence after their communities faced a mass shooting, Gen-Z has proven itself to be a phoenix rising from the ashes. The current and presumptively future generations are given a unique niche in the functioning of our world and every government, from municipal to federal- not to sit and obey totalitarian governments or to abide by heavy polluters running our planet to the ground, but to stand up and make a change, to make a difference. The world's youth have seen the impact "doing nothing" has. So instead, Generation Z is single-handily tasked with making global change, altering the course of more than 150 countries, and posting on Instagram to complete this.

Today's youth has experienced dramatically drastic obstacles from the youth one hundred, fifty, or even ten years ago. As most generations develop and grow up, it is inevitable to have varying age groups understand our world differently, as that is the foundational system that age plays in our society, but Generation Z, the generation born after 1996 (Dimock, 2019), has not only suffered through events that none other generation has, but with the help of social media evolved and grew through the harmful effects of times such as post 9/11 wars, climate change, COVID-19, gun violence, and rapidly changing political systems and international turmoil at unprecedented rates. Using digital platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, and others, the ability to upload pictures or a 30-second video explaining a humanitarian concern five or five thousand miles away from a user can be uploaded anywhere with an internet connection and be seen by millions across the globe. This unique opportunity couples with the unique obstacles that Gen-Z have faced, and for many communities, these platforms offer an escape from crises that have plagued them for decades.

Primary Research Question:

1. Does social media increase the presence of young activists, and how do social media platforms allow activists to gain traction for social movements?

The research question outlined above will guide the analysis and interpretation of the data collected in this study and provide a framework for understanding the impact of social media on the rise of so-called “digital activists” and their role in managing ongoing humanitarian, international, environmental, and social movements.

II. Literature Review

Generation Z has become a focal point for articles and discussion, and mass introspection efforts on the social anthropologic of how a group of teenage and early-twenty-aged young adults can enact social and political change worldwide. By combining peer-reviewed renowned research with societal evaluations from pop culture sources, there can be a clear and concise trajectory of the research paper. For the paper, the terms “Networking, Education, and Advocacy,” huge parts and the pillars that allow social media to be a crucial “wrecking-ball force” for young people, will be further referred to as “NEA.”

II.I. Formal and Cultural Definition of Generation Z and Distinctions

The generations defined

*No chronological endpoint has been set for this group. In this analysis, Generation Z includes those ages 18 to 24 in 2021.
 Gen Z, Millennials Stand Out for Climate Change Activism, Social Media Engagement With Issue

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Generation Z is formally defined as a person born after 1996 (Dimock, 2019), following the millennial generation. They have witnessed world-altering events such as the 9/11 attacks and following repercussions, the climate emergency evolving, the rise of gun violence in the United States, and the COVID-19 Pandemic. Not only have these times earned the generation points for having a “harder than previous generations” (Schrager, 2022), but more specifically, it has opened up a more formal discussion on the impacts of world events on young adults.

Pew Research Center, Visual Representation of Each Generation Start and Endpoints

While other generations, such as Gen-X and Baby Boomers, tend to hind anxiety or depression, gen-z recognize it as a significant problem among their generation (HOROWITZ & GRAF, 2019). Additionally, some groupings and stereotypes they have been involved with drastically shape public opinion and opportunities to advocate for issues that mainly affect them. Characterized by being the most

diverse, on a trend to be the most educated, and known for caring for social movements more (PARKER IGIELNIK, 2020), the issues that matter to this generation are unlike others. Moreover, with these differences from the others, we can see that an overwhelming amount of voting-age members of the generation lean left/democratically (Pew Research Center, 2020).

II.II. Pressure on Gen-Z to Become Politically Active / Activists

Being a part of a generation that grew up in a rapidly changing world- politics, technology, and culture made the members more prone to be politically empowered. For some, it is not about advocating, at least not formally. Youth activism is more about seeing an issue in their local communities and recognizing something different than most legislators– the problem *and* a solution. This unique opportunity presents itself to youth worldwide, coupled with the rise in social media, which is why youth activism and political involvement are so popular. An interview with a then-high schooler revealed that multiculturalism highly impacts advocacy, expressing how her family changed their lives after coming to the United States and, similar to others, lit the flame of wanting to do something more in the context of becoming a force of opposition and altering the status quo. (Falkovich, 2018).

Younger generations more willing than older to give up fossil fuels, phase out gas-powered cars

% of U.S. adults who say ...

II.III. Specific Policies and Social Issues

Fought Over

Due to the cultural traits of Gen-Z leading to the generation leaning predominantly more democratic, most

of the advocacy aligns with these beliefs. For example, a highly debated topic such as whether safe abortion should be available legally to women who need it currently holds a 66% approval rating among Gen-Z respondents aged ~ 16-22 at the time of the poll (Broadbent et al., 2017). Other highly supported topics include climate change among others. According to some reports, the global temperature will increase to an “unfixable point” within the next five years, which induces anxiety or worry among the generation (Dickie, 2023). Through this discovery, we can see that the real issues that Gen-Z advocates for, climate, gun control, etc., are not because they choose to fight for these issues for leisure, but because the other option is submitting to the status quo, but the quo of continuing the eternal cycle of death and anxiety. *That* is why this generation is filled with advocating.

Graph from Pew Research Center showing popular opinion from Gen-Z on Climate Change

II.IV. Ability For Social Media to Connect and “NEA” with Others

Social media, digital platforms, and other internet communications have been a leader in networking, educating, and advocating for social movements and causes worldwide. Regardless of societal class, location (with exceptions), or generational wealth, almost anyone can create a post of pictures or videos in less than one minute. Either from the perspective and information of their communities, they are advocating for change that firsthand affects them- or by using an already existing platform to push for change in an area overlooked in modern media. From five miles or five thousand miles away, social change can be made anywhere in the world. With the assistance of social media, previously obsolete movements,, such as the Uhygur movement in Northwestern China, suffered from an exhaustive attempt to social cleansing through “re-education camps.” However, through social media, activists pushed information about specific Chinese policies that target the ethnic group in a viral 40-second TikTok video (Kashgarian, 2020). Social media is not just a tool for youth to receive makeup tutorials or a shopping list; it is transforming the world and holding governments accountable.

III. Methodology

Data Collection

Qualitative Data:

- News Articles: A comprehensive search and analysis of news articles will be conducted to identify and understand the causes advocated by Generation Z.
- Interviews will be conducted with sociologists and activists specializing in Generation Z-related issues to gather insights into their cultural experiences, political views, and social media usage patterns.
- Case Studies: In-depth examination of specific behaviors, events, or campaigns involving Generation Z will be conducted to provide a rich understanding of their actions and their impact.

Empirical Data:

- Movement Outcomes: Analysis will be conducted on the outcomes of movements that Generation Z has been involved, including assessing the number of volunteers and followers, political bills and policies influenced, and other relevant impact indicators.
- Social Media Metrics: Data will be collected on social media usage rates among Generation Z, including the frequency and duration of usage, platforms preferred, and types of engagement in social movements.

Data Analysis

Qualitative Analysis:

Thematic analysis will be performed on news articles, interviews, and case studies to identify recurring themes related to causes, political views, and social media usage

among Generation Z. This analysis will help generate meaningful insights and develop a comprehensive understanding of their experiences.

Quantitative Analysis:

Descriptive statistics will summarize the social media metrics. Correlation analysis will be conducted to explore relationships between variables such as social media usage and political views. The analysis of movement outcomes will involve assessing numerical indicators to understand the impact of Generation Z's engagement.

Findings and Discussion

The findings from the qualitative and quantitative analyses will be synthesized to provide a holistic understanding of the impact of Generation Z's cultural experiences on their causes, political views, and social media engagement. The discussion will highlight the significance of these findings in the broader context of societal and political change, as well as the role played by youth activists in facilitating international movements online.

Conclusion

The study will conclude by summarizing the essential findings and their implications for understanding Generation Z's cultural experiences, political engagement, and social media usage. It will also provide recommendations for stakeholders such as policymakers, educators, and social media platforms to better engage with and support the youth in advocating for their causes. Additionally, the study will identify potential avenues for further research in this field.

IV. Results

As shown above, the graph gathered from Pew Research Center (see [Section II.III](#) for reference), there can be a clear interpretation of the certain policies most aligned with the Generations' perspective views. Explicitly stated in the graph above, it describes that 54% of Gen Z believe the Earth is getting warmer due to human activity. This is in staunch comparison into the Silent generation and Baby Boomer generations holding a 38% and 45% margin in the same categories, respectively. Through a detailed analysis of each generations social movements, access to social media, and other factors more heavily aligned in detail in [sections III](#) and [sections V](#). Furthermore, as further data from Pew Research Center shows, Generation Z is becoming a more compassionate and understanding generation as each respective member grows up. Citing from the 2019 research post on Pew's website, we can discover that mental health concerns are a large foundational idea on the cultural makeup of Generation Z. This can demonstrate a mutual agreement between mental health, and experiences similar to these comprising why Generation Z are empathetic. Pew has been used thoroughly through this article and is one of the most renowned research firms in the world.

V. Discussion

As thoroughly demonstrated, the overlap between social media usage and unique issues and advocacy efforts in Generation Z is a multi-faceted issue with numerous outlets and avenues that one could analyse, essentially however, it can all be tracked to one issue. Since the start of each member's lives, there has been an event that shifts the trajectory of their early childhood and potentially even their life as a whole, just as an infant or even before they were born. This is not a completely native issue to just this generation, as the Baby Boomer generation for example has suffered the effects and being born in a post WWII America, however the situation in which each party is presented is vastly different. Following events such as The War on Terror, global warming concerns, and other large domestic events with an existing aftershock to this day, Gen-Z uses social platforms, such as Instagram and TikTok to educate current and future generations on social issues.

Due to this precedent of the ability of spreading information worldwide, advocating has taken an uptick in not only political participation online, but a downward trend in the effort needed in order to be proactive for a change. Living in the world of ignorance only serves to perpetuate the lack of education people have towards important global issues. The increased use of social media has served as a civic engagement tool for users to actively be enlightened on different current events happening globally. When one is educated, only then can they serve as an advocate for justice. We see the link between social media education and awareness in contemporary society, this link has only showcased how the platform that social media apps offer such as instgra and facebook help spread knowledge that can be life changing. For instance, we see in the past that users are starting to take to social media to help others in need in third world countries through projects and reels on instagram, Go Fund Me fundraisers through Facebook which have all served to promote welfare causes and raise awareness.

In contrast with generations such as Baby Boomers who have experienced altering events in the start of their lives (WWII), Gen-Z uses these unique experiences to develop a niche into turning these potentially damaging events into a motive for being compassionate and using the opportunities given to them in order to fight for others. Not because there is a reward on the other side of the lure- material or not, but because these major world events which would usually cause a derailment in the plans of an entire generation instead causes a flower to grow after a fire. By seeing how social media fosters creative and personal development to turn misfortunate situations into an opportunity for young adults to advocate and push for change that is affecting them or others is one step closer to “cracking the code” of how digital technology and media will shape future generations.

VI. Conclusion

In conclusion, this research paper has explored the profound impact of social media and Gen-Z advocacy efforts on the evolution of social and international policies. Generation Z, born in the aftermath of significant global events, has harnessed the power of platforms like TikTok and Instagram to amplify their voices and advocate for meaningful change. Through social media, they have been able to connect with like-minded individuals, educate themselves and others, and mobilize social movements on a global scale.

The findings of this study have shed light on the significant role that social media plays in the lives of young activists. It has become a crucial tool for networking, education, and advocacy (NEA) among Generation Z. These platforms have allowed them to transcend geographical boundaries and raise awareness about critical social issues that directly impact their lives and communities.

Furthermore, this research highlights the need for policymakers, educators, and social media platforms to recognize and support the advocacy efforts of Generation Z. By understanding the power of social media as a catalyst for change, stakeholders can create an environment that nurtures and empowers young activists to make a positive impact on society.

However, it is important to note that while social media provides an unprecedented platform for advocacy, it also comes with its challenges. The spread of misinformation, online harassment, and algorithmic biases are among the issues that need to be addressed to ensure a safe and inclusive digital space for young activists.

In summary, the rise of social media and Gen-Z advocacy efforts has reshaped the landscape of social and international policies. Generation Z has embraced these digital platforms as powerful tools for creating awareness, mobilizing movements, and pushing for transformative change. As we move forward, it is essential to recognize the immense potential of social media in shaping the future of activism and to

provide the necessary support and guidance to empower the voices of Generation Z in building a more equitable and just world.